

The Illusion of Explainability with *LLMs* and *LLM*-Agents

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Abstract. The formal linguistic capabilities of *Large Language Models* (*LLMs*) are increasingly intersecting with the field of *Explainable Agency* (*XAg*). The growing adoption of *LLM*-agents has heightened the need to explain their behaviour to users. However, current methods consistently fail to meet desirable properties of human-centric explanations. Moreover, language models are being used to improve traditional agent explainability methods due to their conversational abilities and their resemblance to human responses, yet are often used without sufficient consideration of their limitations. In this paper, we show how the inclusion of *LLM* components in the agent architecture affects the reliability of the explanations produced. We argue that the widespread reliance on *LLMs* in *XAg* is polluting the definition of explanation and explainability. We question current methods of agentic explainability and argue that their risks may undermine trust. Through an architectural analysis and an empirical illustration, we highlight how certain design choices may limit the kinds of explanatory queries that can be reliably answered. Finally, we propose what human-oriented explainability should entail in *LLM*-agents, and we expose the limitations and opportunities of *LLMs*' integration into agent explainability.

Keywords: Agent Explainability · Explainable Artificial Intelligence · Large Language Models · *LLM*-Agents.

1 Introduction

Agentic AI has recently gained significant attention within the AI community, despite the absence of a precise definition. Broadly, it refers to systems that exhibit some degree of autonomy, proactivity, memory, and the capability to act in an environment and adapt their behaviour based on feedback [2,3], a trend largely driven by the increasing availability and performance of *Large Language Models* (*LLMs*) and other Foundation Models [24]. Industrial adoption is accelerating: 62% of organisations surveyed by McKinsey [43] report experimenting

with agents, with 10% already scaling them up in production. In this vein, Gartner predicts³ that by 2028, a third of enterprise software will include some form of Agentic AI-based technology, and 15% of day-to-day work will be carried out autonomously by these systems.

Due to how these systems are being developed [2,24], we are becoming more dependent on *LLMs* (and other models of comparable scale and opacity) as core components for building systems that can act on long-horizon tasks where, in many cases, they will potentially be involved in interactions, decisions or actions that can affect humans in non-trivial ways. In this regard, regulatory frameworks such as the European AI Act [1] explicitly emphasise the need for transparency and interpretability in AI-based systems, particularly when they are deployed in high-risk or decision-critical settings. In Agentic AI, this requirement extends beyond merely justifying isolated outputs or predictions: it concerns the ability to understand, assess, and contest trajectories driven by autonomous decision-making processes. As such systems exhibit increasing degrees of autonomy, providing meaningful explanations of their behaviour becomes a prerequisite for accountability and trustworthiness rather than an optional feature. At the very least, we (humans) need these systems to be *explainable*.

In this paper, we argue that the widespread use of *LLMs* in explainable agency is polluting the definition of explanation and human-centred explainability. First, the use of *LLMs* in agentic systems is distorting the nature of human-aligned explanations. Agentic systems are increasingly complex in operation, and there is currently no method that explains their behaviour in terms of properties desirable for (non-expert) humans. Existing approaches either focus on overly low-level mechanisms or rely on convincing but unreliable post-hoc confabulations. Second, *LLMs* are being misused in traditional agent explainability, without a direct grounding to a precise semantics of explanations. The field of *Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)* is losing focus on faithful and helpful accounts of agent behaviour and is bending to mere linguistic artefacts based on plausibility.

In light of these concerns, we clarify what constitutes a meaningful and useful explanation in agents and agentic systems by revisiting foundational insights from philosophy, cognitive science, psychology, and *Explainable Agency (XAg)*. We examine what explainability as a concept entails in the context of *LLM*-based systems⁴ with the particular focus of this paper being on human-centric explanations of autonomous behaviour (or sequential decision-making), and we discuss the safe and unsafe uses of *LLMs* in agent explainability.

2 Background

The nature of explanation has long been a central topic of inquiry across philosophy, cognitive science, and the social sciences, tracing back to Aristotle’s early

³ <https://www.gartner.com/en/articles/intelligent-agent-in-ai>

⁴ Due to the conceptual ambiguity around agentic terminology (*AI* agent, *LLM*-agent, *e.t.c.*), from now on we adopt the term *LLM*-based system.

reflections on causation. A unifying principle that emerges across these diverse perspectives is the foundational role of *causality*. To explain an observed event is, at its core, to identify and articulate the causal mechanisms that brought it about [30,49,37]. Explaining, beyond the selection of causal factors, looms as an interactive communication act among two participants: the explainer (*e.g.* an *XAI* model) and the explainee (*e.g.* a human user) [30,23] must ideally conform to established rules of conversation. Grice’s maxims [19] are seminal in this regard: communication (and so, explanation) should be tailored to the listener’s needs, and therefore be succinct (*quantity*), reliable (*quality*), relevant (*relation*), and interpretable (*manner*). In adherence to these principles, explaining the behaviour of artificial agents to human receivers entails drawing inspiration from how people construct and interpret explanations of each other’s behaviour [37,18].

According to Malle’s folk-conceptual theory [35], individuals explain others’ behaviour by attributing them mental states such as beliefs, desires, and intentions. If the behaviour is judged to be intentional, people prevalently cite the actor’s *intentions* as causes (*Reason Explanations*), a theory consonant with Dennett’s *Intentional Stance* [11]. Intentions are presumed to emerge from a reasoning process in which the actor is assumed to possess an apparent degree of rationality and awareness of the beliefs and desires informing the decision-making. Other less common explanatory modes of intentional behaviour refer to the background factors that give rise to the intentions above, such as the person’s culture, personality, or prior experience, and the conditions that allowed the intentional action to produce its intended outcome. Although artificial systems lack intrinsic intentionality [41], humans tend to anthropomorphise them, adopt the *Intentional Stance* and ascribe them mental states to make sense of their behaviour [21,18,11]; hence, employing the same theories and desiderata used to explain human behaviour constitutes a pragmatic foundation for human-centric *XAg* [37,38].

From the background analysis, we can infer a set of properties that we can consider minimal for any explainability system that has human explainees as end-users:

- *Causality*: explanations should identify selected causes that brought about the observed behaviour [30,37].
- *Teleology*: for behaviours perceived as intentional, explanations should be framed in terms of the actor’s goals. This is proven empirically when the explainees are humans, as they preferentially explain (and expect to receive explanations based on) actions by referring to what the agent was intending to achieve [35,11].
- *Conversationality*: explanations should adhere to Grice’s maxims of communication [19,23], particularly *Quality*. That is, explanations should *accurately* reflect the actual underlying processes that generated the behaviour. A plausible explanation that is disconnected from the actual process can undermine real understanding and erode trust.

3 Explainability in *LLM*-based Systems

3.1 What Explainability Means in Agentic AI

Several surveys explore the pursuit of explainability in *LLM*-based systems and analyse existing methodologies [10,42,8,51]. Centred on an *LLM* component, agentic systems can borrow state-of-the-art techniques from *LLM* explainability, including mechanistic interpretability [25] and attribution-based methods (*e.g.* [50]). These methods aim to identify *how* specific inputs or internal components influence a model’s output, but the resulting explanations provide no teleological information about the agent’s behaviour. They are often presented in formats that are difficult for users without domain expertise to understand, therefore, failing to meet the needs of human explainees and undermining trust in agentic systems.

In addition, a growing body of work relies on self-rationalisation techniques. The ease of communication in fluent *natural language* (NL) and the user-friendliness of *LLM*-based systems invite the mistaken belief that interaction with these models is a valid approach to obtain explanations of their own “*reasoning*”. Popular approaches use reasoning chains such as Chain-of-Thought [48] and Tree-of-Thoughts [55], where the *LLM* is instructed to think step-by-step and break down its reasoning into sequential and tractable steps. The *LLM* is often fed with few-shot explanation examples or is equipped with an external knowledge base to retrieve factual information, thereby mitigating hallucinations. The generated thought process is ultimately claimed as a form of self-explanation.

These explanatory utterances resemble human-like explanations [27]. Still, this appearance may reflect the *LLM*’s exposure to large *corpora* of human-written text during training, as well as its ability to adapt through in-context learning from few-shot examples. Nonetheless, the resulting narratives violate Grice’s maxims:

- Quantity: the outputs are excessively verbose; although length-reduction strategies exist (*e.g.* by setting a maximum number of tokens), they can degrade performance in generated responses [29]. An explainee who receives such lengthy reasoning (in which the *LLM* may often change its reasoning, tune or approach) will take a shallow look and come to wrong conclusions. More so, this precludes explainability in fast-moving contexts.
- Manner: besides quantity being unintelligible, there is no assurance that the *LLM* reasoning will be intelligible to a human explainee. Moreover, in providing “thoughts”, the *LLM* may confabulate or invent facts supporting their reasoning [44,31], confusing the explainee (even if the outcome was correct).
- Quality: the confabulation in the previous point similarly applies, with *LLM* providing wrong information. In addition, thoughts of the *LLM* are not guaranteed to align with actions or plans. This is especially true in extended plans: the reasoning for later steps of a plan precedes the initial steps; as such, the thoughts are less relevant than the plan as written. Furthermore, the faithfulness of *LLM* rationalisations has been shown to be

unreliable [45,6,51,46,27] even when following the *LLM*-enthusiast’s advice to prompt the model to think step by step.

3.2 What Explainability Should Mean in Agentic AI

The explainability of a system should account for all questions one can ask of it. When integrating an *LLM*, it can either generate imperative actions or provide declarative statements for downstream algorithms. In a black-box architecture, the kinds of questions that could be asked about its internal processes become hidden and appear less important. A proposal addressed this with a *ladder of intentions* [17], which exhaustively categorises questions to ask of any architecture in terms of causality and folk psychology. In this framework, the agent architecture is decomposed into declarative and imperative components situated at different levels of abstraction, the *rungs* of the ladder, from the highest level N (the designer’s intention) to the lowest level 0 (the action to be executed). Declarative components include the agent’s beliefs (S_i), which can be provided by a learning process (E), and imperative components (I_i) are processes that select lower imperative components I_{i-1} using information S_i . Explanations can be extracted by following the causal connections of imperative and declarative components up the ladder, from individual actions I_0 to designer intentions I_N , posing three explanatory questions at each level i :

- Intentional ($Q_1(i)$): Why I_i ?
- Weakly Epistemic ($Q_2(i)$): Why is S_{i+1} fulfilling I_{i+1} ?
- Strongly Epistemic ($Q_3(i)$): Why believe S_{i+1} ?

In systems that include epistemic and/or imperative components implemented with *LLMs*, the designer acknowledges that explanatory queries about those components become unanswerable. Given the training based on autoregressive next-token prediction, an *LLM*’s goal is not to preserve formal truth, but to generate text that sounds *like* a reasonable continuation of prior words [22]. To achieve this goal, the model compresses multiple nearby concepts into coherent-sounding utterances. When precision conflicts with fluency and caution, the model sacrifices correctness because its objective function rewards plausibility and pedagogical form rather than logical entailment [34]. Because the *LLM* does not learn to understand the meaning of language, one cannot establish reliable causal connections between the model’s inputs and its outputs [56] *in the sense required for purpose-oriented explanation*. The only possible teleological explanation is that the model’s behaviour reflects the designers’ intentions.

To illustrate how the degree of explainability of a system varies with the presence of *LLMs*, we analyse three architectures that contain *LLM*-components, we map them onto the ladder of intentions, and highlight unanswerable explainability queries.

The first example is a **virtual household robot** (A_1) equipped with an *LLM* that receives user commands specifying domestic tasks [5]. Given a list of possible tasks in its context, the *LLM* identifies the user’s requested chores

and anticipates additional related tasks. For instance, if the human asks A_1 to *dry clothes*, the *LLM* may predict that ironing and folding are also desired. The resulting set of tasks is encoded as a *Planning Domain Description Language* (*PDDL*) problem and provided to a *PDDL* planner, which generated a sequence of actions to fulfil the tasks jointly. The plan is executed within a simulation environment and can be interrupted or modified by the user via prompts.

Fig. 1: Declarative and imperative components of the household robot architecture. Components marked * are (partially) composed of / generated by an *LLM*.

In the ladder architecture for A_1 (Figure 1), I_0 denotes the space of actions available to the agent (*e.g.* to move, to cook). S_1 represents the robot’s percepts (*e.g.* current location) and information obtained from the *VirtualHome* environment, such as the spatial configuration of rooms within the house.

At the higher level, I_1 corresponds to the *PDDL* plan responsible for selecting an action based on the epistemic state S_1 . This imperative process is selected by a *PDDL* solver (I_2), which deliberates over the declarative knowledge encoded in a *PDDL* domain file (S_2) that specifies action pre- and post-conditions and domain information. Moving one level upward, S_3 contains the user task request(s), the list of possible tasks, and the *PDDL* program with the goals to be achieved by A_1 . Given the complete list of tasks and user prompts, an *LLM* serves as an imperative component that generates declarative statements (E), namely, *PDDL* goal specifications. I_3 represents the replanning loop triggered by user inputs, which relies on S_3 to configure the *PDDL* solver in I_2 to generate or revise plans in response to the user’s requests.

From the ladder characterisation of A_1 ’s architecture, we identify one unanswerable explainability question:

- $Q_3(2)$: *Why does A_1 believe to have these goals (S_3)?* S_3 contains the tasks that A_1 is expected to achieve, resulting from an imperative process in which an *LLM* maps user-requested and auxiliary tasks to *PDDL* goals. Since it

is not possible to identify reliable causal relationships between the user’s request and the *LLM*’s outputs, the understanding of *why* A_1 pursues a given set of goals is insufficient, and the question cannot be answered.

Fig. 2: Declarative and imperative components of the Voyager architecture

The second example is *Voyager* [47], building on the initial analysis presented in [17]. *Voyager* (A_2) aims to survive in an open-ended Minecraft environment by acquiring skills and completing tasks. The system’s architecture includes a *LLM* component that produces a curriculum of increasingly complex tasks and a skill library. When assigned a task, A_2 uses an *LLM* to generate code to acquire skills, and the loop of code generation (and correction) and skill acquisition continues until the current task is achieved. If A_2 persistently fails to fulfil the task, the curriculum generator assigns a new one.

In A_2 ’s ladder (Figure 2), I_0 corresponds to the set of possible actions expressed as executable code. S_1 represents A_2 ’s perceptions, environmental information from the *Mineflayer* API, and execution-level feedback provided by a code interpreter. In the upper level, I_1 represents the skill (some code to select actions) that A_2 has to execute based on S_1 . This skill is the result of an imperative process (I_2) where an *LLM* determines which skill to generate or refine with respect to S_2 , which includes the current task, the skill library, and *LLM*-generated information about previously completed and failed tasks.

At the highest level, I_3 represents the automatic curriculum generator, which determines the order of tasks taking into account the designer-given directive prompt and optional in-context information about the game Minecraft.

We identify four unanswerable explainability questions: two concerning A_2 ’s skill generation and execution, and two addressing its task prioritisation and selection.

- $Q_3(1)$: *Why does A_2 believe the provenance of the available skills, possible tasks, and feedback in S_2 ? S_2 includes feedback from earlier failures in*

achieving skills generated by a *LLM* and integrated into the execution code as comments. Since prior experiences cannot be traced to the generated code, the question cannot be answered.

- $Q_2(1)$: *How does S_2 fulfil the intent of the skill generator I_2 ?* As above, it is not possible to causally explain why the skill generator produced the given code from S_2 .
- $Q_1(2)$: *Why does A_2 aim to program the skill generator I_2 ?* The curriculum generator is an *LLM*, so there are no guarantees that the curriculum is factually based on the priority level of each task coming from S_3 .
- $Q_2(2)$: *How is S_3 fulfilling the intent of the curriculum generator (I_3)?* It is not possible to causally trace how the designer’s prompt and game specifications conditioned I_3 .

The third example is a member (A_3) of the artificial society of **Generative Agents** [39]. A_3 is designed to simulate human behaviour and social interactions in a town-like environment populated by other generative agents. Its architecture is based on a process orchestrating a set of components: a *LLM* for inter-member communication and environment interaction, conditioned on a summary of A_3 ’s identity (*e.g.* name, occupation); a memory of A_3 ’s experiences in NL; a retrieval mechanism for selecting relevant memories; a reflection process to generate self-reflections; and a planning component to generate plans from the reflections, both of which are recurrently stored as part of the memory.

Fig. 3: Declarative and imperative components of the Generative Agent architecture

The first level of the ladder contains low-level actions (represented as emojis) and NL utterances (I_0). I_0 is influenced by A_3 ’s memories (S_1), which are represented in NL and include percepts, dialogue, plans or reflections. I_0 is selected by a *LLM* (I_1) based on a subset of those memories.

Climbing one rung higher, there are statements about memories (S_2), such as recency of a memory, the provenance of reflections (a memory originated from other memories), or the relevancy with respect to a current perception. While these statements are used to provide I_1 with the subset of retrieved memories through a purely arithmetic process, the provenance of these memory properties (*e.g.* relevance, importance) is derived from an epistemic process E which is *LLM*-based.

Statements produced in S_2 are then integrated into S_1 , becoming part of the long-term memory of the agent for future use.

In the highest level, I_3 represents the orchestrator that selects what the agent should focus on (I_2) based on A_3 's architecture (*e.g.* to do planning the first thing in the day, or reflections every 100 memories). S_3 is composed, as of now, from purely designer-given statements (such as when it is good to generate reflections or plans). We identify 3 unanswerable explainability questions for A_3 :

- $Q_1(0)$: *How does I_0 fulfill the intent of I_1 ?* Given the prompt in I_1 , there is no direct way to answer why it acted as it did.
- $Q_3(0)$: *What is the provenance of memories in S_1 ?* For percepts, it is clear, but reflections/plans come from *LLM*-based generations (in E).
- $Q_3(1)$: *Why does A_3 believe the relevance and importance of memories and the origins of reflections (S_2)?* I_2 uses a *LLM*-based process to compute relevance and importance to decide which memories to put in I_1 's prompt.

4 *LLMs* in Agent Explainability

4.1 *LLMs* as Explanation Generators

Literature on *LLMs* for *XAg* [7] indicates that most approaches use *LLMs* to extract and/or interpret explanations elicited by the original methods and to dialogue with the user. Some methods summarise observed agent behaviour into a graphical model and present it to the *LLM* for explanation [52,32], or prompt the language model to summarise behavioural traces itself [54,4]. Others use *LLMs* to explain reward decomposition results [33,36], to invoke and interpret *ad-hoc* explainability tools depending on the user request, and to provide dialogue-based explanations in *Belief-Desire-Intention* (BDI) agents [13].

These methods fail to rigorously constrain either the *LLM*'s elicitation and interpretation of explanations and/or the user's interaction, granting the model considerable freedom and exposing the resulting explanations to intrinsic *LLM* limitations that are detrimental for explainability, such as *hallucinations*, prompt sensitivity, epistemic failures [44], lost thread in conversations and verbosity [28]. *LLMs* for *XAg* should be deliberately used as structured parsing interfaces interceding between explanation-elicitation methods and users, and vice versa. This mediation ought to be governed by predefined templates for user requests and a shared vocabulary with a standard syntax between the method and the *LLM*, thereby, by design, reducing the semantic contribution of *LLMs*. To our knowledge, only a few methods [20,14] show promise in this direction.

4.2 LLMs as Explanation Evaluators

Recent works advocate the use of *LLMs* for automatic evaluation of explanations, positioning them as a cost-effective and scalable alternative to user studies (e.g. [9,12,57]). The main argument of using *LLM-as-a-Judge* is that, with appropriate prompting, language models can *approximate* human judgements and preferences when evaluating explanations. One must not forget, however, that the objective of human-centred explainability is to enable the user to decide whether to trust a model or not, and user studies aim to validate the reliability of the produced explanations and their usefulness in improving the users’ understanding of the agent [26]. As discussed in Section 3, *LLMs* are indifferent to the factual accuracy of their outputs, and there is no assurance that the sentences produced are the result of the reasoning they appear to express. This severely compromises their suitability as trustworthy substitutes for human evaluators.

5 Experiments

In Section 3, we discuss theoretically how the reliability of explanations for a system’s behaviour is affected by the presence of *LLMs* in the architecture. In these experiments, we evidence this by comparing explanations for the behaviour of an *LLM*-based system and of a *Reinforcement Learning (RL)* agent acting in the same environment and achieving similar performance. Given the importance of teleology in explanations, as motivated in Section 2, we rely on a state-of-the-art *XAg* method, *Intention-aware Policy Graphs (IPGs)* [16], to extract teleological explanations from observed behaviour. The code is available at <https://github.com/HPAI-BSC/reliable-xai>.

5.1 MiniGrid Environment

The selected environment belongs to the MiniGrid family, which provides single-agent, deterministic, 2D GridWorld environments that follow the standard *OpenAI Gym API*. We consider the environment `MiniGrid-Unlock-v0`⁵, where the agent has to open a locked door. The agent operates under partial observability and can only perceive a 7×7 grid centred on its current position. Its observations are provided as a dictionary of three elements:

- *image*: a $7 \times 7 \times 3$ tensor encoding each visible tile in the grid, where each tile stores information about the object it eventually contains, i.e. its type, colour, and state;
- *direction*: the agent’s current orientation;
- *mission*: the string `open the door`.

Figure 4 shows an example frame from the environment. The agent operates in a customised discrete action space consisting of six possible actions (0-5): turn

⁵ <https://minigrid.farama.org/environments/minigrid/UnlockEnv/>

Fig. 4: Example frame of the environment. The agent is represented by the red triangle, and the highlighted region represents its partial observation.

left, turn right, move forward, pick up an object, drop the object being carried, and toggle (*e.g.* open a door). The agent cannot move onto a tile that already contains an object.

To solve the task, the agent must find and pick up the key, navigate to the locked door, and use the toggle action to unlock and open it. The episode terminates either when the agent reaches the target or when the maximum number of steps (100) is reached. The reward function returns 1 upon successful goal attainment, a penalty proportional to the number of steps taken, and 0 otherwise.

5.2 Agents

RL Agent We train a *RL* agent using the *Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)* algorithm [40] under the Stable Baseline3 implementation⁶. Training uses only the agent’s partial observations of the environment, and is performed over 500000 timesteps and a fixed random seed of 42. All other hyperparameters of the algorithm are left at their default values. The agent is evaluated across 10 episodes with different random seeds, achieving an average success rate of 0.97 ± 0.01 in completing the task.

LLM-based System In this system, the inference is performed using the Qwen3-32B model [53], with a temperature of 0.8 and a maximum number of output tokens of 8192. This system operates on a NL-descriptive version of the MiniGrid environment, instructed with the following initial prompt:

```
Plan a sequence of actions for an agent in a grid world.
### Instructions:
1. Analyse the state and goal.
2. Check history for loops.
3. Output a plan of up to 3 actions to move toward the goal.
```

Once an episode starts, at each step, the actor receives the current observable state in NL (its position, orientation, and visible objects), the task goal, the set of available actions in NL, and the last three state-action pairs. Based on this information, the model outputs a plan of up to three⁷ actions, along with a reflection on past moves and a brief reasoning of the proposed actions. The

⁶ <https://stable-baselines3.readthedocs.io/en/v1.0/modules/ppo.html>

⁷ This choice was made to balance the number of *API* calls with the actor performance.

planned actions are converted to their numerical format and executed in the environment. The actor is evaluated over 10 episodes with different random seeds, achieving an average success rate of 0.92 ± 0.03 in completing the task.

5.3 Intention-aware Policy Graphs

IPGs [16,15] are a *post-hoc*, model-agnostic *XAg* approach to produce explanations in terms of an agent’s desires and intentions. The method starts from building a probabilistic graphical model from observations of an (opaque) agent interacting within an environment. Each node of the graph corresponds to a discretised state s , and each edge represents the probability $P(s', a|s) = P(a|s) * P(s'|s, a)$ of transitioning from s to s' upon the execution of action a .

A desire d hypothesised to guide the agent’s behaviour is formalised as the execution of a specific action a_d within a desirable state region S_d . The agent’s intention $I_d(s)$ to fulfil a desire d from a state s is defined as the probability of reaching the desirable state region and executing a_d starting from s , and is computed as the sum of the probabilities of all possible sequences of states and actions starting from s and terminating in (s', a_d) , where $s' \in S_d$.

To build the *IPG* for the systems under analysis, we collect 200 observations of the agents’ behaviour (up to 100 steps each) and map them into discretised state-action trajectories, which are then used to build the policy graph. The discretised action space is similar to the original one, except that the actions pick-up, drop, and toggle are collapsed into a single action defined *interact*. A state in the environment is discretised into three variables, each taking a single value. `hold_key` denotes whether the agent has a key or not. `key_nearby` represents the closest action toward the key, and can be turn left, turn right, go forward, or none (if the agent already holds a key or none is visible in the surroundings). Similarly, `door_nearby` represents the closest action toward the door. Two desires are hypothesised to motivate the system’s behaviour:

- The desire to collect the key: the desirable state region consists of states in which the actor is not carrying a key, and the optimal action to obtain the key is to interact with it. The action to be performed is to interact.
- The desire to open the door: the desirable state region consists of states in which the actor is carrying a key, and the optimal action to open the door is to interact with it. The action to be performed is to interact.

5.4 Explainability Results

Global Intentions The interpretability of an agent’s behaviour and the reliability of the explanations produced are assessed using two metrics for a desire d [16]: the *attributed intention*, defined as the probability of being in a state where the intention to fulfil d is greater than a threshold $C \in (0, 1]$ (interpretability), and the *expected intention*, defined as the probability that, once attributed, an intention of d will be fulfilled (reliability). Higher C values increase the reliability of the explanations, since only states with a high probability of desire fulfilment

are considered to have an active intention. Lower C values improve interpretability by attributing intentions to a broader set of states. We set $C = 0.5$ to balance both metrics.

Fig. 5: Comparison of intention metrics with $C = 0.5$. *Any* refers to states where an intention of at least one of `get_key` or `open_door` is attributed.

Figure 5 shows intention metrics for the *RL* agent and the *LLM*-based system, providing a global overview of the intentions behind their behaviour. Although the two systems achieve similarly high task performance, the intentions attributed to their behaviour differ substantially.

The *RL* agent exhibits high interpretability and reliability: an intention of *any* of the two desires is attributed to 98.8% of the states, and it is fulfilled in 78.7% of these cases. When attributed, the desires `get_key` and `open_door` are frequently fulfilled (in 72.8% and 81.2% of cases, respectively), with occasional failures that may reflect suboptimal decisions.

On the other hand, intentions can rarely be attributed to the *LLM*-based agent’s behaviour, making its behaviour difficult to interpret. Intentions are attributed in only 15.8% of the states, indicating that the system is rarely in a state from which it will fulfil either `get_key` or `open_door`. The extremely low attributed intention probability for `get_key` could be due to the system not inferring properly the need to obtain a key before opening the door, as this requirement is not explicitly stated in the initial prompt⁸, or that the system may attempt to reach the key but struggles to do so given the *LLM*’s limited planning skills. The system fulfils this intention in 52.8% of the cases. From analysis of the *LLM*’s output traces, we observe that when facing the key, the actor first attempts to move to the same grid cell as the object before collecting it, which is not possible since the environment allows only one object per grid cell.

Similarly, `open_door`’s attributed intention probability is low, which can be a consequence of the difficulty in obtaining the key, or of the *LLM*’s limited planning capabilities. Unlike `get_key`, the attribution of an intention to open the door is highly reliable, as it is always fulfilled.

⁸ Similarly, the *RL* agent does not receive any explicit reward for collecting the key.

Fig. 6: Trajectory of the *RL* agent to solve the task with environment seed 0.

Fig. 7: Evolution of the *RL* agent intentions during the episode. Vertical lines refer to the fulfilment of intentions of the corresponding colour.

Local Intentions We initialise a new episode and observe the two systems interacting with the environment to solve it.

The trajectory of the *RL* agent while performing the task is illustrated in Figure 6. The observed behaviour aligns with the computed intentions shown in Figure 7: initially, the agent is primarily committed to collecting the key, with a low intention to open the door. Intention values increase until the agent collects the key; at this point, intention `get_key` drops to zero since it has been fulfilled, and `open_door` increases until fulfilment.

The trajectory of the *LLM*-based system while performing the task is illustrated in Figure 8. The system eventually collects the key and opens the door, successfully completing the task. However, the behaviour leading to this outcome differs from the *RL* agent and exhibits less consistent teleological structure.

When positioned in front of the key (step 5), the agent first attempts to move to the grid cell occupied by the key before performing the interaction required to pick it up. Since the environment does not allow the agent to move onto a cell already occupied by an object, this intermediate action has no effect and results in inefficient behaviour. In practice, the system often performs this unnecessary step, which contributes to the relatively low intention values associated with the desire to obtain the key.

Once the key is successfully collected, the intention `get_key` drops to zero because the corresponding desire has been fulfilled. After that, the system proceeds

Fig. 8: Trajectory of the *LLM*-based system to solve the task with environment seed set to 0.

Fig. 9: Evolution of intentions of *LLM*-based system during the episode

towards the door and eventually unlocks it, although the trajectory followed is suboptimal compared to the *RL* agent. The intention to open the door increases after the key is obtained but remains relatively low for much of the trajectory, reflecting that the agent frequently occupies states from which fulfilment of the hypothesised desires cannot be predicted with high probability. In particular, the agent performs some steps that are highly inconsistent with the goal of reaching the door (such as turning away in step 7).

Overall, while the *LLM*-based system is sometimes able to complete the task, the resulting trajectories in such cases are weakly goal-directed (*i.e.* executing actions that cannot be explained in terms of goals). This results in behaviour that is more difficult to interpret than that of the *RL* agent. Please note that the findings presented here are preliminary; in future work, we will extend the experimentation to more models and complex environments.

6 Discussion

Our analysis has highlighted a *tension* between the demand for agent explainability and the reliance on plausible text answers to questions. A first open challenge for the community is therefore **to systematically distinguish between genuine explanations and the mere *illusion of explainability***. When relying on *LLMs*, for instance, plausible language can easily mask the absence of causal, teleological or process-faithful grounding. Explainability cannot be guaranteed *a posteriori* if the underlying system lacks a clear causal/intentional structure. This raises the question of **how agent architectures should be designed so that explainability is preserved even when *LLM* components are integrated**. If preserving full explainability becomes untenable, **in which components of an agent is relinquishing explainability acceptable (and thus *LLMs* are a possibility), and in which ones does it result in harm to system trustworthiness?**

Our initial experimentation further suggests that even when task performance is comparable, the resulting behaviour may differ substantially in interpretability. In the setting we considered, albeit simple, the behaviour of the *LLM*-based system was often poorly goal-directed, resulting in lower interpretability. These findings should be considered preliminary, but they highlight *how* differences in behavioural structure can affect the extent to which agent behaviour can be reliably explained.

Therefore, agent designers play an important role: **systems should make explicit commitments about *what* they can and cannot explain, and be explicit about the limits of the explanations they provide**. As discussed, there are methods for identifying the scope of explanations that can be produced.

In the meantime, and while *LLM* explainability cannot be reliably benchmarked, **explainability should be treated as an architectural constraint on agent design**, rather than as a mere *post-hoc* linguistic feature. To ensure that the use of *LLMs* in explanations is genuinely valuable, a promising first step is to deliberately reduce their semantic contribution by design.

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